

Production of Biodiesel and Hydrogen storage material from Chicken Feathers

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ABSTRACT:

Biodiesel is a form of diesel fuel derived from biological sources such as poultry waste, animal fat, vegetable oil, soybean oil, etc. It is renewable, biodegradable and is a potent alternative for fossil fuels. In this paper, we can see that chicken feathers, a form of poultry waste is used as a raw material for producing biodiesel, which is collected from processing units. Chicken feathers contain 91% Keratin protein, 1.5% water and 7.5% fats which is extracted from the waste by subjecting it to the process of pyrolysis, followed by collection which yields biodiesel product. It is seen that upon pyrolysis of 500g of feathers, a yield of 5.5ml of oil is obtained. Not only should this but if carbonized chicken feather be able to store hydrogen as well better than carbon nanotubes. The use of chicken feathers as raw material reduces the cost of production and also provides an effective way of waste management. We know that the world population is rising at an alarming rate and with it the need of natural resources is also increasing. Moreover, excessive use of fossil fuel leads to toxic emissions of Greenhouse gases that contribute to Global warming. Therefore, it is essential to develop an alternative natural energy source and Biodiesel is one such fuel.

Keywords: Biodiesel, Pyrolysis, Chicken feathers, Greenhouse gases, Keratin protein

1. INTRODUCTION

With constant rise in world population, the need for natural resources is also rising at an alarming rate. This is leading to the exploitation of natural resources of which fossil fuels are major part. Also, excessive use of fossil fuels leads to toxic emissions that are major contributors of global warming. Hence, it is essential to develop alternative source to meet the energy demands and also control pollution. Biodiesel is one such potent alternative for fossil fuels¹. Biodiesel refers to long chain Monoalkyl esters of animal fats and vegetable oils¹. It is also known as green fuel and it is a renewable fuel as it can be generated from various sources. It also reduces the emission of GHG (greenhouse gasses) by 45-60% compared to fossil fuels upon combustion. Combustion of biodiesel emits lower aromatic and Sulphur content along with a reduction of 90% in total unburnt hydrocarbons (HC). Compared to fossil fuels, production of biodiesel is a labour-intensive work hence; it helps in creating employment in rural areas and helps in regional development¹.

Types of biofuels

- 1st generation biofuel: It includes Ethanol and biodiesel which are obtained directly from biomass that are more often edible. Ethanol is synthesized by the fermentation of sugars (C6 compounds) by using yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*). Feedstock such as sugarcane, corn, potato waste, whey and barley are used for the production of bioethanol. The major disadvantage seen in the case of first-generation Biofuels is that the raw material supply can have conflicts with food supply.

Fig.1. Year-wise Consumption of Fossil Fuel in terms of Direct Energy (TWh)²

- 2nd generation biofuel: It is produced from a variety of biomasses including lignocellulosic biomass which makes up the largely available non edible materials from plants. Lignocellulosic alcohol, butanol and mixed alcohol are the few Biofuels obtained under this generation. The major advantage that they have is that they are not competing with food supply and also brings down the cost of production.
- 3rd generation biofuel: these fuels are produced from algal biomass, which has a distinct growth yield when compared to lignocellulose biomass. Chlorella species of algae are majorly used because of their high lipid content of about 60– 70%.
- 4th generation biofuel: these fuels are synthesized from genetically modified biomass of algae for better CO₂ absorption and higher yield of lipids.

2. Review of Literature

Generation of biofuels

This paper contains information about the 1st and 2nd generation biofuels, their sources, their drawbacks. The 1st gen biofuel includes bioethanol, biodiesel and biogas. Their sources are biomass like food crop and organic waste. Its drawback is that due to the production of 1st gen biofuels the amount of crops drastically decreased and with this the price raised by leaps and bounds which led to unavailability of food to poor. Then emerged 2nd gen biofuels which is characterised by production of cellulosic fuel and Fischer – Tropsch fuel. This overcame the drawbacks of 1st gen as the source was replaced with lignocellulosic feedstock which makes up for the abundant and low-cost, non-food material available from plants. But it too has disadvantage and its is that it isn't able to match the growing demand for liquid fuels. Hence, there came the need to find a new generation of biofuels to overcome these drawbacks³.

Classification of biofuels

This paper contains wide information about economic and environmental aspects of biofuels. This gives us an insight about how biofuel affects a country's economy and environment. It helps reducing greenhouse gases emissions (GHG), increasing rural economy and also generates employment as production of biofuel is labour intensive⁴. This paper also provides us with information regarding classification of biofuels into traditional and modern biofuels based on usage. In older days, traditional biofuels such as cow dung, wood, crop residues and charcoal were utilized to provide energy for cooking and heating. While traditional fuels themselves being available in nature had null cost, it costs the user time and energy invested in search of fuelwood⁴. Then came the modern fuel which comprised of liquid fuels like bioethanol and biodiesel which had main application for transportation and

generation of electricity. The liquid biofuels are not affordable by poor people as they are still not economical due less production. These are the few points that we find very effective for our study⁶⁻⁷.

Chicken feathers as a source of fats, oils and hydrogen storage material

This research paper provides an insight to the composition of chicken feathers¹. It is essential to confirm that chicken feathers have fat content that can be converted into oils thereby enabling us to use the feathers as a raw material for the synthesis of biodiesel. Chicken fibers are majorly composed of feather keratin which is about 91% of the feather content. Fat content in the feather fibers is estimated to be 1.5% and the rest is the water content which is 7.5%. According to this data it is clear that there is fat content in the chicken feathers that can be extracted by subjecting it to the process of pyrolysis. Also, pyrolyzed chicken feathers(PCFF) fibres which if prepared by a two-step process demonstrates a significant H₂ adsorption uptake due to their microporous nature. Considering their large availability, cost and H₂ storage capability, PCFF can be significant, environment friendly and bio-renewable candidate to address the H₂ storage problem⁸.

Fig. 2. Contents of chicken feather

Design of pyrolysis reactor

This paper includes not only the production of Biodiesel but also the formation of pyrolyzed chicken feathers to store hydrogen by using same process Energy which is only possible by the TWO-REACTOR system of the reactor. A biodiesel reactor, that is designed to produce the best quality biodiesel and a pyrolysis reactor with an afterburner chamber to prevent energy loss. They are so, that the heat from pyrolysis can be used for transesterification process. This was also discovered that adding woodchips as purification element of biodiesel (for separating biodiesel and remains of glycerol) would be the cheapest and the best solution. Pyrolysis reactor not only contains the main heating chamber but also contains a collecting chamber which collects Biodiesel and condenses it^{1,9}.

3. Methods / Testing and Redesign

The first step in this project investigation is to determine the correct chemical composition of chicken feathers and chicken feather meal, since the protein content is very important for pyrolyzing chicken feathers in order to get good hydrogen storage, and fat content for processing chicken feather meal into biodiesel^{1,10-11}.

Experiment I - determining the chemical structure by extraction of oil from chicken feathers-Sohxelt's method

The preparation of chicken feathers: A portion of chicken feathers is first cut into smaller pieces and then homogenized, ground and placed in a porous cellulose thimble. The thimble is placed in an extraction chamber, which is suspended above a flask containing the solvent

(here it is used hexane C_6H_{14} as a solvent) and below a condenser. At the end of the extraction process, which lasted 3 hours, the flask containing lipid is removed¹².

Experiment II - extracting oil from chicken feather meal

Weighed 806.3 g of feather meal sample and stirred it from a time to time. The water is heated up to $100^\circ C$ for about 2 hours. The absorbed fat melts and floats on the surface of water layer¹².

Experiment III - The acid number is measured by titration process.

Here 1g of fat and 50mL of diethyl-ether is taken and then it is mixed. 3 drops of phenolphthalein is added. The mixture is then titrated until the colour change appears¹².

Pretreatment process

Sulfuric acid is used as catalyst and methanol as alcohol for the pre-treatment. The esterification process parameters are calculated for different molar ratios, amounts of acid catalyst based on the weight of FFAs. 1.86 ml of 96% H_2SO_4 are used (35% of H_2SO_4 , calculation based on the FFA level) and 30:1 methanol ratio or 55.8 ml of methanol^{6,13}.

Determining the recapture

The titration for determining the acid number of the oil is repeated and then proceeded to the transesterification reaction. The recapture turns to be 20% of methanol (volume) and 0.5% of NaOH (mass) on the amount of fat extracted^{6,14}.

Working principle of Pyrolysis reactor and biodiesel reactor

This section deals with the different parameters with the working of reactor

Independent variables:

Type of chicken feathers, amount of chicken feathers, amount of chicken fat

Dependent variables:

Amount of carbonised chicken feathers, time, amount of biodiesel

Equipment used:

test tubes, boiling tubes, beaker, Erlenmeyer flask, round-bottomed flask, dropping funnel, filter funnel, Lirbig funnel, Graham condenser, graduated cylinder, pipette, graduated pipette, burette, thimble, crucible, muffle furnace

Materials used for two-reactor system:

Pyrolysis reactor: Steel drums, metal pipes, mesh grate, pyrolysis tray, glass wool, faucet

Biodiesel reactor: Steel drums, metal pipes, mesh grate, pyrolysis tray, glass wool, faucet

Safety measures: Disposing all chemical waste properly, working in well-ventilated area, dressing properly with lab coat on.

4. Results

The main objective of this work is to determine the right composition of chicken feathers and meal made from them and to create the best conditions for production of biodiesel from chicken

feather meal and for pyrolyzing the feathers. After many experiments it has come to the best conditions. In this part will be all the results gained from the methods and materials that is

used¹⁵.

Experiment I - Soxhlet extraction, the most secure way to get the best overall result, proved to be effective in determining the fat content of the chicken feathers.

Table 1: Fat content of chicken feathers¹²

Experiment extraction of	Mass of ground feathers for Soxhlet's extraction	Mass of fat extracted	Fat content (%)
	12.721g	0.233g	1.8%
The mass of chicken feather meal	The mass of fat gained	Fat content (%)	
788.3g	108.5g	13.76%	

II - oil from chicken feather meal
Table 2: Fat content of chicken feather meal¹²

Table 3: Fat content of chicken feather meal¹²

From this experiment fat content is	Result	Fat Content in (%)
	This paper Result	13.80 %
	Result 1	12.00 %

and water found so the rest is protein which is approx.90.2%.

These results show that chicken feathers are perfect storage of hydrogen since the protein content is greater than 90%. The net result is carbonized feather fibres, which can absorb as much or perhaps more hydrogen than carbon nanotubes or metal hydrides.

The acid number proves to be too high for conversion to ester, so a pre-treatment processes us required, but here it is done in one-step unlike other processes that are usually two-step. Density is also tested, acid number and rate conversion for chicken feather biodiesel and it is then compared to biodiesel samples made from other kinds of fats¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Table 4: acid value of chicken fat¹²

Treatment stage	Acid value in Percentage
Before	9.8%
After	2.2%

Table number

Biodiesel	Acid number of the produced biodiesel and another biodiesel sample in (mgKOH/g)
Chicken Feather	0.80
Biodiesel 1	0.44

5: Acid of

biodiesel¹

Biodiesel	Rate of conversion (%)
Chicken Feather Biodiesel	91%
Biodiesel 1	78%

Limitations

One of the setbacks of this project is that chicken fat has to go through a pre-treatment process in order to decrease the FFA number. That is of course an increment in cost but since it manages to conduct an one-step pre-treatment process it is still very cheap to use¹⁹. Another dilemma is: Is biodiesel worth of production when the prices of oil are decreasing? Well, according to the latest researches, the oil supplies found till now, are expected to run out in about 40 years. That is why biodiesel is definitely worth of production¹⁹. While testing the carbon nanotubes they came to be a great solution for hydrogen storage, no con. Also, density of this biodiesel is high so it can be lowered for use. In future, it can be planned to measure the IOD number and INDEKS of refraction of this biodiesel. It can be planned to test the pre-treatment process with 20% H₂SO₄ too and add a filtering element to our system, which will make it cost effective and a better and efficient fuel to use¹².

6. Conclusions

In summary, the properties of chicken feathers show us that Chicken feathers are effective for production of fuel storage, in this case hydrogen storage material and also for biodiesel production and can be proved by the results which shows lower ash content, moisture content, volatile matter content, higher biochar yield, fixed carbon content¹¹.

The two-reactor system used has the key role in producing good-quality hydrogen storage material and biodiesel. It is energy-efficient, cost-effective and environment friendly¹¹.

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